

A STUDY ON WOMEN EMPOWERMENT: A KEY FACTOR TO ACCOMPLISH SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

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Abstract :

Women empowerment is a controversial matter for many years. Women had faced lots of difficulties to get equal status as men. Women were perpetually had treated as a slave for many years. With every passing year, statues had changed slowly and gradually in the favor of women. In the current scenario, we can able to see the women's had engrossed with the admirable position in the various fields. Despite immerse success still today women face lots of discrimination and harassment in society. When we talk about women empowerment it is all about the supremacy and competency sharing the identical rights.

Key words: *Women empowerment, sustainable development, gender equality, factors for empowerment, role and importance*

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Introduction :

Women, who account for more than half of the world's population, have always been - and continue to be - the deciding factor in the quality of life and well-being of their families. It represented among the world's most accessible groups, as access to resources and power is skewed heavily in favour of men. Women's empowerment is a cross-cutting development issue that will not be realised until it is tackled in a multifaceted manner. The role of women in sustainable development must be acknowledged. Women have an important part in their children education and socialisation, including teaching them responsibility and caring. Women's involvement in the family, community, and society as a whole must be free of socio-cultural and religious norms that hinder women from participating. Women's empowerment is not only a goal in itself, but it is also a critical component of sustainable development in economic, social, and environmental progress. Gender equality and women's empowerment are human rights that are at the heart of development and the Millennium Development Goals' implementation. Women's empowerment and the fulfilment of women's rights have become more important in attaining sustainable development in recent decades. This is evident in a variety of international agreements and standards. International norms and standards on women's and girls' human rights and gender equality provide a strong foundation for expanding

action to increase women's critical role in achieving sustainable development. The focus is on women's empowerment as a critical step toward gender equality and sustainable development. It begins by examining the notions of women's empowerment and sustainable development, as well as how they are related.

Women's empowerment and gender equality are critical for our society's long-term growth. Many international leaders and academics have claimed that without gender equality and women's empowerment, sustainable development is impossible. Environmental protections, social and economic development, are essential for sustainable development. Women would not feel as integral to the development process as males if women were not empowered. The whole participation of both men and women is usually thought to be necessary for growth. Only acknowledging men's involvement will not lead to long-term growth. When it comes to women development, empowerment must involve more conscious choices for women. However, the country would be unjust and social transformation would be impossible without female equality and empowerment. As a result, researchers believe that women's empowerment is a critical component of development and one of the most important contributions to development. Women will not be treated equally in the workplace until they are included on an equal footing.

Sustainable development is extensively described as improvement that meets cutting-edge wishes without compromising the cap potential of destiny generations to satisfy their wishes. Sustainable development is the principle precept of all rules and measures aimed toward constructing a society primarily based totally on freedom, democracy and recognize for essential rights, and selling identical possibility and unity inside and among generations need to be.

Sustainable Development Goals :

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were formulated at the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development in 2012. The purpose was to come up with a set of generally applicable goals that balanced the three components of sustainable development: environmental, social, and economic development . The Sustainable Development Goals are based on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). The magnitude and ambition of the new global Agenda are demonstrated by the Sustainable Development Goals and 169 sustainable development goals adopted at the United Nations Headquarters in New York on 2015, and which went into effect on January 2016. The new SDGs go well beyond the MDGs, addressing the core causes of poverty as well as the universal need for development that benefits everyone. Each SDG has precise objectives that must be met by 2030. The Sustainable Development Goals are based on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs). Unlike the MDGs, which were exclusively meant to be implemented in developing countries, the SDGs apply to all countries. "They aspire to accomplish all people's human rights, as well as gender equality and women's and girls' empowerment." "Sustainable development" is defined as "development that fulfils current demands without jeopardising future generations' ability to satisfy their own needs." It is an economic, social, and environmental development that assures human well-being and dignity, environmental integrity, gender equality, and social justice in the present and future.

Women Empowerment :

These days women's empowerment in India is one of the most constructive instruments for development. In the current scenario, women are working enthusiastically in different part of the world as a leader. Women come across with diverse roles and responsibilities on each passing day, additions to these women's are also considered as the backbone of the nation. Women's empowerment refers to their liberation from the shackles of social, economic, political, caste, and gender oppression. It entails allowing women to make their own life decisions. Women's empowerment does not imply 'deification of women,' but rather the replacement of patriarchy with parity. It is a process that entails both the building of a discrimination-free environment for women and the strengthening of women's ability to take charge of their own lives and actively participate in the necessary changes in our society.

Objectives :

- To gain a better understanding of the concepts of sustainable development and women's empowerment
- To study role & importance of women's empowerment for a sustainable future.
- To analyze the factors responsible for women empowerment.

Research Methodology:

The descriptive research design is used in this study. Research is purely on secondary data. The data was gathered through research papers, journals, websites, HR blogs, and survey reports published by various research organizations.

Literature Review :

1. Maherukh Khan and Shabana Mazha (2017)

This article focuses on women's empowerment as a critical step in achieving gender equality and, as a result, sustainable development. It begins by examining the concepts of women's empowerment and sustainable development, demonstrating how they are linked via the perspective of intra- and intergenerational justice.

2. Dolly Sharma. Dr. Jaya Dwivedi (2015)

The author highlights that in their daily lives, women are faced with a variety of responsibilities. They are largely responsible for domestic chores; however the current situation necessitates rural women's long-term development. This may be accomplished by empowering these women via adequate education and training. In this study researchers attempts to focus on the appropriate training that rural women should receive in order to utilise natural resources. Enhancement of efficiency and productivity, as well as the production of variety, may be used to bring about strategic approaches. Controlling some social and economic aspects can help to bring this out.

3. Sudershan Kumar Pathania (2017)

This paper aims to provide an overview of several concepts like Equity, Sustainable Development, Empowerment, Gender Equality, and Human Rights According to the author, in order to develop women as catalysts for long-

term growth, their roles in the home, community, and society as a whole must be free of socio-cultural and religious traditions that limit women's participation. For this work, secondary data will be used. The purpose of this study is to highlight the critical role of women as partners and beneficiaries in sustainable development.

4. Dr. Meenakshi Lohani. Prof. Loai Aburaida (2017)

In this research paper author concludes that economic, social, cultural, and environmental problems must be addressed in a holistic and integrated manner. From a gender perspective, it is critical not to view gender equality just as a socio-cultural issue, but to address it in the economic and environmental domains as well, recognising gender equality as a cross-cutting goal for achieving sustainable development.

5. Kokane J.P., Shinde S.Y. (2020)

The researcher discusses ideas such as women's empowerment and the elements that contribute to empowerment, and concludes that women are empowered when they have access to all of the options that are accessible to them, including those in education, profession, and lifestyle. It entails actions such as boosting women's position via education, awareness, literacy, and training. Women's empowerment entails equipping and empowering women to make life-altering decisions in the face of societal challenges. The researcher focuses on the critical and vital aspects that contribute to women's empowerment in India.

Factors Responsible for Women Empowerment :

Education :

Women's education is their first layer of protection against the life-threatening situations that a conventional lifestyle maintains. With a good education, a woman's position can rise above the constraints of motherhood. Women's and girls' education progress leads to a postponement of marriage and, as a result, a reduction in the size of their families. Enrolment and retention of girls in basic formal and non-formal education should be prioritised through incentive methods such as free textbooks, midday meals, school bags, science kits, uniform, scholarship, residential and hostel facilities, and the elimination of gender discrimination in the curriculum. So UNESCO conference in 1962 underlined the significance of the get entry to of women and girls to technical and vocational schooling for financial and social development.

Elimination of gender discrimination :

Another key aspect is gender discrimination. Women should be treated with the respect and position that they deserve in society in order to attain their goals. To attain the aim of empowerment, they should be given the chance to participate actively in decision-making at all levels and management processes. In India, the problem of gender discrimination has slowed the progress of women's empowerment. Gender inequality must be addressed in all areas of action. To achieve the goal of empowering women, women must be given the opportunity to participate actively in decision-making at all levels and in decision-making procedures. To fulfil their destiny, individuals must gain the respect and importance that they are entitled to in society based on merit.

The Transformation is Being Led by the Media :

The media has a vital role to play in projecting and propagating related concerns, particularly in India's case of women empowerment. The countless programmes on women's prestige revealed that the media allows her spouse to treat her with a great deal of dignity and respect. He can change his mindset and help her in the home to minimize tension and worry. The media has a critical role in healing husbands' and other family members' attitudes and communication styles toward women.

Conduction/ organization of Women's Development Program :

A training programme based on action in the village or in rural India, as well as vocational programmes and growth-oriented entrepreneurship development programmes, must be organised to help women become self-sufficient after becoming self-employed by improving their efficiency and capacity to make quick decisions. Other enactments ACTs relating to marriage, succession, divorce, adoption, dowry, moral safety, or protection against sexual harassment must be implemented in order to serve the goal of women empowerment in India.

Changes in Women's Attitudes :

Women should empower themselves by being conscious of their oppression, taking initiative, and seizing opportunities to change their situation. Empowerment must originate from the soul. Women must take charge of their own empowerment by adopting a new mindset.

Organization for Awareness Programmes :

State and National level commissions for women, Non-Governmental Organisations, ICDS Programmes, should adopt e-awareness, the Taskforce for women & children Development DWACRA (Concerning Development of Women & Child in Rural Areas), women's rights, human rights, a marketing campaign approximately legal rights, training approximately saving schemes, populace training, environmental training, rehabilitation programmes with all integrity and solemnity.

Role and Importance of Women Empowerment for Sustainable Development :

Gender equality :

Whether in government, industry, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), or research institutes, gender equality is a moral obligation - it's just the 'right thing to do.' Gender discrimination persists in many cultures, economy, political, and social organisations across the world. Women and girls are subjected to intolerable levels of discrimination and abuse, which is not only unethical, but also stops them from fully participating in society and decision-making.

Women offer a Unique Viewpoint to the Table :

Women are more exposed to environmental degradation and climate change than males, but they also have unique views, concerns, and reform ideas. Environmental sustainability will remain a distant objective unless they are taken into account, with women empowered to participate fully in decision-making at all levels.

Counting the invisible contribution :

This draws us to the third reason for embracing women's empowerment into sustainable development, which goes deeper into the underlying causes of both issues: in most societies and economies, women's unpaid work and natural resources are not accounted for, and thus are not valued appropriately in our economic, political, and social systems.

Ensures society's holistic development :

In India, women's empowerment is one of the most important phrases for the country's overall growth. There is nothing wrong with contributing to the advancement of civilization. Women work in a variety of fields in the corporate sector, including medicine, engineering, and other fields. Apart from taking part in the domain of technology, they are vigorously engaging in security services such as police, navy, military, etc. All these before-mentioned services are moving the community to another level.

Determine their Intelligence Level :

There has been a consistent rise in women's empowerment during the last decades. Women must have self-esteem, self-assurance, and the ability to select their own demands and requirements. People should not be classified based on their gender, and it has no value. Women are still paid less, are expected to cook, and are controlled by their families. Women's empowerment is required to overcome these difficulties and play an autonomous role in society.

Competent of alleviating unemployment :

Unemployment is one of the most prevalent challenges in emerging societies. According to the study, women make up half of the population. Women's unemployment and uneven possibilities at work in India may be eliminated with the support of women's empowerment. When women are faced with unemployment, their whole potential is squandered. Women must be given equal opportunity in order to fully utilise their power and potential.

Conclusion :

Before gender equality can be achieved and maintained, women must be "empowered" to close the "gender gap" and provide a level playing field for both men and women. In one way or another, all of the SDGs deal with gender sensitization. Women's contributions in all disciplines should be bolstered by guaranteeing their complete economic development. Women's empowerment is no longer only a lofty goal; it is now a critical missing link in the quest for long-term development. Women reinvest up to 90% of their earnings into their families on average. Women have more money to spend on food, housing, and education when gender inequality is reduced, which is critical for poverty reduction and long-term development. Empowering women is critical for long-term growth and a shared future. Reinforce commitments to provide women's equal rights, access, and leadership opportunities in the business, society, and political decision-making. If sustainable development is to thrive, women must be empowered and gender equality must be ensured.

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